

Supporting Information for:

Semi-Transparent Quaternary Oxynitride Photoanodes on GaN Underlayers

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III. References

I. Experimental Methods

1.1 Preparation of sapphire (Al₂O₃)/GaN substrate

2 μm-thick gallium nitride (GaN) epitaxial structure was grown on 2-inch double side polished Al₂O₃ (sapphire) substrate, with maximum cut-off 0.25°. The growth was conducted in low pressure metalorganic vapor phase epitaxy reactor (LP MOVPE) – AIX 200/4 RF-S, employing the consecutive precursors: trimethylaluminum (TMAI), trimethylgallium (TMGa) and ammonia (NH₃), while hydrogen (H₂) and nitrogen (N₂) were used as the carrier gases. In the MOVPE system a temperature was in situ controlled by emissivity corrected pyrometry using a Laytec EpiCurve TT system. The epitaxy process was conducted at approximately 1373 K and 200 mbar. After the process, the GaN/Al₂O₃ structure was cut into 10 × 15 mm sample pieces.

1.2 Fabrication of LaTiO₂N thin film on Al₂O₃/GaN

A modified method for La₂Ti₂O₇ thin film preparation was employed to make the precursor solution.¹⁻³ Briefly, 5 ml of 2-methoxyethanol (99.8%, Sigma-Aldrich), 4 ml of acetic acid (99.9+%, Alfa Aesar) and 1 ml of acetylacetone (99%, Merck) were mixed together by stirring. 1.0825 g of La(NO₃)₃·6H₂O (99.9%, Alfa Aesar) was dissolved into above solution and the mixture was stirred for 1 h. Afterward, 0.8509 g of titanium(IV) butoxide (97%, Sigma-Aldrich) was added dropwise under strong stirring, the mixture was stirred for additional 3 h to get clear solution containing ~0.25 M of La and Ti in molar ratio of 1:1. The solution was used to fabricate films by spin coating at 3000 rpm for 20 s on Al₂O₃/GaN substrate in air, the film was dried on a hot plate of 573 K for ~5 min to remove organic constituents. Afterwards, the substrate was calcinated at 773 K for 1 h to decompose all organic components forming oxide. The oxide was converted to LaTiO₂N oxynitride by nitridation under flows of NH₃ (15 mL min⁻¹) and H₂ (5 mL min⁻¹) at 1148 K for 2 h at a ramping rate of 10 K min⁻¹.

1.3 Fabrication of SrTaO₂N thin film on Al₂O₃/GaN

The precursor solution was prepared by using a modified process for Sr–Ta–O perovskite thin film.⁴ Inert atmosphere was used to handle the compounds for solution preparation. In short, 0.304 g of Ta(OCH₂CH₃)₅ (99.95%, Alfa Aesar) was added dropwise to 0.154 g of Sr(O₂CCH₃)₂ (Sigma-Aldrich), then 3.0 mL of acetic acid (99.9+%, Alfa Aesar) was added to the above mixture. The slurry was stirred for 1 h to obtain a clear solution containing ~0.25 M of Sr and Ta in molar ratio of 1:1. It should be noted that the solution should be freshly synthesized before each use. The solution was used to fabricate films by spin coating at 3000 rpm for 20 s on Al₂O₃/GaN substrate in air, the film was dried on a hot plate of 573 K for ~5 min to remove organic constituents. Afterwards, the substrate was calcinated at 773 K for 1 h to decompose all organic components forming oxide. The oxide was converted to SrTaO₂N oxynitride by nitridation under flows of NH₃ (15 mL min⁻¹) and H₂ (5 mL min⁻¹) at 1148 K for 2 h at a ramping rate of 10 K min⁻¹.

1.4 Atomic Layer Deposition of Ta₂O₅

Tantalum pentoxide thin films were synthesized via atomic layer deposition (GEMStar XT; Arradiance, Inc.) using pentakis(dimethylamino)tantalum(V) (PDMAT, 99.99%; Sigma-Aldrich) and H₂O (HPLC grade; VWR Analytical) as precursors. Ultra-high-purity N₂ (99.999%, Airgas) was used as the carrier gas in the reactor and was controlled by an automated mass flow controller (20 sccm) for the entire deposition. The sample substrates were placed in the chamber held at 423 K, while the PDMAT precursor cylinder was heated to 379 K for the duration of deposition. Each cycle of the deposition consisted of a 100 ms precursor pulse of PDMAT, a chamber purge of 15s, a 15 ms H₂O pulse, and a second purge of 25s. This sequence was repeated a total of 600 times. This procedure resulted in a Ta₂O₅ film of roughly 20 nm (by cross-sectional scanning electron microscopy) for films grown for calibration on a silicon wafer coated with a thermally-grown oxide layer.

1.5 Characterization

X-ray diffraction (XRD) patterns were recorded with a Panalytical X'Pert Pro system configuration with Cu K_α radiation at grazing incidence mode to minimize the contribution related to the substrate.

Surface morphology was characterized using a scanning electron microscope (SEM, JSM-7000F, JEOL) at accelerating voltage of 15 kV.

Ultraviolet-visible (UV-vis) transmittance spectra were collected by using UV-2600 (Shimadzu) spectrometer in the wavelength range of 300-900 nm.

1.6 Photoelectrochemical measurements

Photoelectrochemical (PEC) measurements were carried out in a three-electrode PEC cell (WAT Venture) with a potentiostat (PalmSens4, PalmSens BV) in 0.1 M NaOH aqueous solution (pH 13) under AM 1.5G simulated sunlight. The AM 1.5G simulated solar illumination was generated by a solar light simulator (class-AAA 94023A, Newport) with an ozone-free 450 W xenon short-arc lamp. The as-prepared film on the Al₂O₃/GaN substrate, a 1 M Ag/AgCl electrode, and a platinum wire were used as the working, reference, and counter electrodes, respectively. The measured potentials versus 1 M Ag/AgCl have been converted to the reversible hydrogen electrode (RHE) scale according to the Nernst equation ($E_{\text{RHE}} = E_{\text{Ag/AgCl}}^0 + 0.059 \times \text{pH} + E_{\text{Ag/AgCl}}$). Linear sweep voltammetry (LSV) curves were performed at a scan rate of 10 mV s⁻¹ under chopped illumination. Chronoamperometry curves were recorded at a constant bias 1.23 versus RHE under chopped illumination.

II. Supplemental Figures

Figure S1. SEM micrograph at low magnification of Al₂O₃/GaN/Ta₃N₅.

Figure S2. Chronoamperometry curve of Ta₃N₅ film measured at 1.23 V versus RHE in 0.1 M NaOH under chopped AM 1.5G solar simulated light (100 mW cm⁻²).

Figure S3. SEM micrograph at low magnification of LaTiO₂N film on Al₂O₃/GaN substrate.

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